

Rac-7a

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-153-3-rac-20%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	20	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 153 3 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/28/2022 3:45:37 PM CST		
Date Processed:	9/24/2022 10:20:57 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.739	4198081	49.86	366819
2	9.282	4221651	50.14	341014

Asy-7a

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-153-3-ASY-20%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	50	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 153 3
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	7/28/2022 4:05:15 PM CST		
Date Processed:	9/24/2022 10:19:09 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.772	12089275	95.75	1059478
2	9.339	535956	4.25	50405